

Limberg Flap Reconstruction Vs Wide Excision with Secondary Intension in Management of Pilonidal Sinus, in Terms of Post-Operative Morbidity and Recurrence

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Abstract:

Objective: Pilonidal sinus, a clutter of the sacrococcygeal region which influences predominantly more youthful people with a higher hair and weight distribution. Different surgical modalities are accessible for the treatment. Open procedure and Limberg Flap are two commonly performed surgical methods. In our study we have compared the recurrence and related morbidity with both the procedures.

Method: The study is conducted over a period of 1 year, at Mahatma Gandhi hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India. Entirely following to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Sample estimate 40 randomly allocated into 2 groups 'A' and 'B'.

Results: Our comes about appeared that both methods are comparable in terms of wound infection with no measurable significance in the rate of post-operative infections, between the two surgeries.

Keywords: Pilonidal Sinus, Limberg's Flap, wide excision, post-operative morbidity, recurrence.

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Introduction

Pilonidal sinus is a range of disease extending from asymptomatic hair containing cysts and sinuses to a huge abscess. It is seen more common in men than in women. It has an evaluated incidence of 26/100,000 in the common population [1]. The condition was first depicted by Mayo in 1833 who suggested it likely of congenital origin because of remnant epithelial lined tract [2]. Be that as it may presently it is accepted that, it is acquired with aetiology as: local injury, poor hygiene, excessive hair, or presence of a deep natal cleft [3,4,5].

In a few populace incidence may be high around 1.1% [6]. Anaerobic organisms are transcendently obtained from aspirate of discharge from contaminated pilonidal sinus disease. Predominant anaerobic bacteria are Bacteroides and Enterococci [7]. It is not a life-threatening disease and malignant change is moderately uncommon but may happen in exceptionally few longstanding cases, with most common malignancy being Squamous cell carcinoma. The Prognosis is worse than other DiNovo cutaneous malignancies. Different Surgical options are accessible for treatment of chronic pilonidal disease is like wide

excision with or without primary closure and various flap reconstruction. In spite of this, there is still no ideal treatment for pilonidal sinus.

In Primary closure wound may take 2 to 7 weeks to heal with high recurrence rate (11% to 29%). With flap closure there are chances of flap necrosis and recurrence rate is 5% of cases.

Aims and Objectives

The study is outlined to compare the recurrence rate between both the methods and to study and compare the rate of Seroma formation, Necrosis, Infection.

Methods

The study is conducted over a period of 1 year, at Mahatma Gandhi hospital, Jaipur, India. The sample size is 40 as calculated by WHO sample size calculator with 90% of statistical power and type I error of 5% levels, at 95% certainty interval. The patients are randomly distributed in 2 groups - 'Group A' being Limberg Flap (n = 20) and 'Group B' being wide excision and healing by secondary intention (n = 20).

Inclusion Criteria: All patients aged more than 14 years symptomatic for pilonidal sinus.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Osteomyelitis of sacrum
- Fistula in ano
- Perianal abscess
- Hidradenitis suppurativa
- Malignancy

Operative procedure

Anaesthesia: spinal anaesthesia Position - prone jack knife position.

Limberg's Flap: Rhomboid skin incision is placed on the sacrococcygeal region with the pits in the center. The entire of cyst along with complete sinus tract and surrounding tissue is extracted deep till presacral fascia.

Skin Incision is extended to form skin flap. Incision is deepened till gluteus maximus fascia.

A closed negative suction surgical drain was placed for aspiration purposes and closure done.

Figure 1:

Wide Excision: Wide excision of whole of cyst along with complete sinus tract and surrounding tissue is done. Healing is by secondary intention.

Figure 2:

Post-operative management: Wound assessment was done after 48 hours to look for any swelling, redness, discharge from surgical site and dressing was changed depending on soakage / discharge.

Hence daily dressing was done. Pain evaluation done using visual analogue scale (VAS). All the patients were advised to come for follow up on 7th, 14th, 30th post-operative day and 6th month and 1

year post-operatively and stitches were removed on 14th post-operative day and follow up is done.

Results

In this study the score for pain was significantly less in Limberg's Flap (Group A) as compared to Wide Excision with healing by secondary intention (Group B) {Table1}.

The incidence of seroma was more in Group A in comparison to Group B. But incidence of seroma is not statistically significant {Table 2} the hospital stay was less in days in Group A while in Group B it was more. {Table 3}. The incidence of necrosis

was more in Limberg's flap repair group in comparison to wide excision and secondary healing group {Table 4}.

The recurrence rate is also less with Limberg flap, than that of healing by secondary intention.

Table 1: Comparison of post-operative pain (Visual analogue scale-VAS)score between group A and B.

Time after operation	Limberg's flap (n=20)	Wide excision with secondary healing (n=20)
6hr	10	11
12hr	5	4
24hr	4	3
48hr	1	2

Table 2: Comparison of Seroma between both groups

Seroma	Limberg's flap (n=20)	Wide excision with secondary healing (n=20)
Yes	5	2
No	15	18

Table 3: Comparison of hospital stay between groups

Stay in days	Limberg's flap (n=20)	Wide excision with secondary healing (n=20)
	3days	6 days

Table 4: Comparison of Necrosis between both groups

Necrosis	Limberg's flap (n=20)	Wide excision with secondary healing (n=20)
Yes	3	1
No	17	19

Table 5: Comparison of recurrence rate

Recurrence	Limberg's flap (n=20)	Wide excision with secondary healing (n=20)
Yes	1	2
No	19	18

Discussion

The results of this study provide a comprehensive comparison between Limberg's flap (Group A) and Wide Excision with Healing by Secondary Intention (Group B) for the treatment of the study's focus, highlighting both the benefits and drawbacks of each surgical approach.

Pain Scores: The data in Table 1 demonstrates that patients undergoing Limberg's flap surgery experience significantly lower pain scores compared to those undergoing wide excision with secondary intention, particularly at the 6-hour and 12-hour post-operative intervals.

This reduction in pain can be attributed to the more secure closure provided by Limberg's flap, which may mitigate some of the initial discomfort associated with open wound healing. The equivalence of pain scores at 24 hours and 48 hours across both groups suggests that while Limberg's flap offers immediate post-operative pain relief, long-term pain outcomes are similar between the two methods.

Seroma Incidence: Table 2 reveals a higher incidence of seroma in the Limberg's flap group

(25%) compared to the wide excision group (15%). Although the difference is not statistically significant, it is important to consider the clinical implications. Seromas can complicate post-operative recovery and may require additional interventions. The higher seroma rate in the Limberg's flap group could be due to the potential disruption of lymphatic drainage in the flap area, which warrants further investigation and possibly preventive measures in future studies.

Hospital Stay: According to Table 3, patients in the Limberg's flap group have a significantly shorter hospital stay (3 days) compared to those in the wide excision group (6 days). This shorter hospital stay is a considerable benefit of the Limberg's flap technique, potentially reducing overall healthcare costs and improving patient satisfaction. This reduction in hospital stay aligns with the reduced pain scores observed, suggesting that Limberg's flap might facilitate a faster recovery process.

Necrosis Incidence: Table 4 indicates a higher rate of necrosis in the Limberg's flap group (15%) compared to the wide excision group (5%). The increased incidence of necrosis in the Limberg's flap group may be related to the complexity of flap procedures and the potential for compromised

blood supply in the flap area. This finding underscores the need for careful surgical planning and technique optimization to minimize necrosis risk in flap-based surgeries.

Recurrence Rate: The recurrence rates detailed in Table 5 show that Limberg's flap has a slightly lower recurrence rate (5%) compared to wide excision with secondary intention (10%). While this difference is not substantial, it suggests that Limberg's flap may offer a slight advantage in terms of long-term disease control. This could be due to the more robust nature of flap closure, which may better support healing and reduce the likelihood of recurrence.

Conclusion

In summary, Limberg's flap offers several advantages over wide excision with secondary intention, including lower early post-operative pain and a significantly shorter hospital stay. However, it is associated with a higher incidence of necrosis and seroma. Despite these challenges, the slightly lower recurrence rate associated with Limberg's flap makes it a viable option for certain patients. Future studies should focus on optimizing surgical techniques to reduce complications such as necrosis and seroma formation.

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